

Manchester Journal of Transnational Islamic Law & Practice

About

The Manchester Journal of Transnational Islamic Law & Practice (formerly the Journal of Islamic State Practices in International Law) was founded in 2005. The Journal is independent of any State, school of fiqh or institutional affiliation and has a diverse and global editorial board. It is indexed on Scopus and available both in electronic and printed forms.

Aims of the Journal

The principal objectives of the Manchester Journal of Transnational Islamic Law & Practice (MJTILP) are to provide a vehicle for the consideration of transnational forms of Islamic law and practice. Transnationalism in Islamic law is taken broadly as communications and interactions linking Islamic thoughts, ideas, people, practices and institutions across nation-States and around the globe. In recent times, research in Islamic law has shaped narratives based on nation-States, demographics, diasporic communities, and ethnic origins instead of developing around a central core. Contemporary issues of Islamic law are increasingly linked to geographical locations and ethnic or parochial forms of religious beliefs and practices. Expressions like American, European, British, Asian, and Arab Islam have widely gained acceptance.

Despite the growing importance of dialogue to develop shared understandings of issues facing Islamic law and proposing coordinated solutions, the contemporary research and scholarship has not developed harmoniously and remains piecemeal and sporadic. Researchers and practitioners of Islamic law are drawn from a wide variety of subjects and come from various regions of the world but have insufficient institutional support for sharing information and comparing experiences. Innovation in various strands and paradigms of Islamic law and practice is stifled because there are limited spaces where evolutionary, collaborative and interdisciplinary discourses can take place. This in turn hampers the ability to build on past research and record best practices, negatively impacting a consistent and orderly development of the field. There is a need to constitute a world community of Islamic law scholars based on interactions and aspirations moving across linguistic, ethnic, geographical and political borders.

The MJTILP is inspired by the need to fill these gaps. It provides a platform to legal and interdisciplinary scholars and researchers for critical and constructive commentaries, engagements, and interactions on Islamic law and practice that are built upon configurations in contemporary contexts. It welcomes contributions that look comparatively at Islamic law and practice that apprise and inspire knowledge across national boundaries whether enforced by a State or voluntarily practiced by worldwide Muslim communities. We are equally interested in scholarships on encapsulated cultural worlds, diaspora, identity and citizenship that are embedded and circumscribed by religious ties. As it has been the practice of the journal since its establishment in 2005, it also has a specific interest in issues relating to the practice of Muslim States in international law, international law issues that may concern Muslim countries, and all aspects of law and practice affecting Muslims globally.

Printed and bound by Antony Rowe Ltd. Eastbourne UK
ElectronicPublications.Org

Manchester Journal of Transnational Islamic Law & Practice

MJTILP

Volume 20

Issue 3

2024

ISSN 2633-6626

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Performing Salah in the Metaverse: Analysing the Perspectives of Ahl al-Hadith and Ahl al-Ra'yi within the Intersection of Technology and Religion

Mursyid Fikri*

Indriana**

Abstract: Prayer, as a fundamental pillar of Islam, is at the intersection of religious tradition and modern technological innovation. In the era of the rapidly evolving metaverse, questions arise concerning the validity and legitimacy of performing prayers in this digital environment. This article explores the perspectives of two prominent Islamic legal schools of thought, Ahl al-Hadith and Ahl al-Ra'yi, on the practice of prayer within the metaverse. By employing epistemological and ethical approaches, the article analyses the responses of these schools to the opportunities and challenges posed by the integration of technology into religious practices. The findings indicate two primary religious responses regarding the validity of prayer in the metaverse. The first response rejects the legitimacy of performing prayer in the metaverse, while the second accepts it under the condition that the virtual space meets the criteria necessary to serve as a legitimate place of worship.

Keywords: Performing Salah; Metaverse; Ahl al-Hadith; Ahl al-Ra'yi; Religion; Islam

I. INTRODUCTION

Islam is a religion that deeply understands that humans are social and dynamic beings who are constantly undergoing changes and developments in various aspects of life. Islam also pays great attention to *muamalah*, which are social aspects that affect human daily life.¹ The development of human life is inseparable from the contribution of rational thought. The intelligence of reason makes humans the most special creatures on earth, because with the potential of reason they have, humans are able to continue to develop ideas, make various innovations, creations, and other activities.² The thoughts and schools of law that developed in a period cannot be considered independent without considering the context of the previous period. This is due to the close relationship between the present and the historical process and socio-cultural conditions in the place where these schools emerged.³

Metaverse technology has the potential to form a simulated environment that supports the practice of Muslim worship. This technology allows interaction and simulation in a social context related to Muslim worship in a virtual environment.⁴

The presence of metaverse as a form of technology that is able to change the sensation of human experience in cyberspace, not only dealing with a cell phone screen but we are able to communicate in real time with everyone in the metaverse space in real time using a

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¹ Djoko Hartono, *Pengembangan Ilmu Agama Islam Dalam Perpektif Filsafat Ilmu (Studi Islam Di Era Kontemporer)* (MQA Surabaya 2015).

² Misbahuddin Samsuddin, Kurniati, 'Dialectics of Reason and Revelation: Islamic Law Reform in the Perspective of Legal Sociology' (2023) 22 (2) *Expose: Journal of Legal Research and Education* 56, 67.

³ R. Ambo, 'Aspek Sosio-Kultural dalam Kitab-kitab Fikih' (in Indonesia) ['Socio-Cultural Aspects in the Books of Jurisprudence'] (2013) *DIKTUM: Journal of Sharia and Law* 82, 92.

⁴ Reza Rachmadtullah, M. S. Zulela, and Mohamad Syarif Sumantri, 'Development of Computer-Based Interactive Multimedia: Study on Learning in Elementary Education' (2018) 7 (4) *International Journal of Engineering and Technology (UAE)* 2035, 2038.

metaverse avatar.⁵ this creates many opportunities and challenges in many industrial fields, one of which is in the field of education. The application of metaverse itself has been widely used in the education industry.⁶

In the development of Islamic law, there are two main schools in the method of legal *istinbat* (deducing laws): Ahl al-Hadith and Ahl al-Ra'yi. The differences between the two were influenced by factors such as teachers, socio-cultural conditions, and geographical factors. Ahl al-Hadith is a group that strongly adheres to the Sunnah of the Prophet. In contrast, the Ahl al-Ra'yi group focused more on future issues and based the law on thought and *ijtihad* (juristic reasoning).⁷

The implications and dynamics associated with prayer in the metaverse open up a variety of questions and reflections related to the relationship between religion and technology in contemporary society. The practice of prayer in a virtual environment presents challenges and opportunities that require a deep understanding of ethics, spirituality and cultural aspects.⁸

Previous research has revealed that the utilisation of metaverse technology in religious contexts introduces new dynamics in religious experiences. Metaverse platforms open up opportunities to hold virtual worship gatherings, enabling the participation of worshippers from different geographical locations. The Christian view of "digital ecclesiology" reflects efforts to integrate cultural and spiritual elements into online worship practices. Technology enables direct communication between congregations to be easier, on a wider scale, and with greater clarity.⁹

On the one hand, the adoption of technology in worship reflects the progress and adaptation of religion to changing times.¹⁰ However, this implication also triggers broader debates about the boundaries between the virtual and real worlds, and their impact on authentic religious experience. Moreover, the relevance of the practice of prayer in the metaverse in debates about the relationship between religion and technology highlights the complexity of the interaction between religious traditions and technological innovation.

This discussion raises interesting questions about how Islam, in particular, can view technology as a tool to enhance the depth of individual spirituality and strengthen connectedness within the community, while still maintaining important traditional values. As such, the exploration of prayer in the metaverse becomes not only a case study of the intersection of religion and technology, but also a journey of thought that explores views based on the approaches of Ahl al-Ra'yi and Ahl al-Hadith.

⁵ Pablo Javier Ortega-Rodríguez, 'De La Realidad Extendida Al Metaverso: Una Reflexión Crítica Sobre Las Aportaciones a La Educación' (in Indonesian) ['From Extended Reality to the Metaverse: A Critical Reflection on Contributions to Education'] (2022) 34 (2) Ediciones Universidad de Salamanca EUSAL 189, 208.

⁶ Yavuz Toraman, 'User Acceptance of Metaverse: Insights from Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and Planned Behavior Theory (PBT)' (2022) 12 (1) EMAJ: Emerging Markets Journal 68, 75.

⁷ Muttaqin Choiri, 'Posisi Ra'Y Dalam Pembentukan Hukum Islam' (in Indonesian) ['The Position of Ra'y in the Formation of Islamic Law'] (2015) 12 (4) AL-'ADALAH 743, 754.

⁸ M Baihaqi Fadhil Wafi, Nuzula Ilhami and Taufiqurohman Taufiqurohman, 'Transformasi Perilaku Beragama Masyarakat Muslim Kontemporer: Fenomena Al-Qur'an Di Era Digital' (in Indonesian) ['Transformation of Religious Behavior Among Contemporary Muslims: The Phenomenon of the Qur'an in the Digital Era'] (2022) 11 (1) IN RIGHT: Jurnal Agama dan Hak Azazi Manusia 40, 54.

⁹ Heidi Campbell A, 'Digital Religion, Understanding Religious Practice in New Media Worlds vol. 01' (London and New York, 2012) 57.

¹⁰ Andika Andika, 'Agama Dan Perkembangan Teknologi Di Era Modern' (in Indonesian) ['Religion and Technological Development in the Modern Era'] (2022) 2 (2) Religions: Journal of the Study of Religions 129.

This article is organised by analysing various opinions and fatwas from the Ahl al-Hadith and Ahl al-Ra'yi within the framework of legal arguments. This methodology provides a foundation for establishing legal rulings on the practice of Salah in the metaverse, presenting a novel contribution to the field and introducing a new dialectic between technology and religion. Part II of the article provides a conceptualisation of metaverse according to Qur'an; part III examines the potential differences between Ahl al-Hadith and Ahl al-Ra'yi views on prayer in the metaverse; and part IV of the article probes the validity of the metaverse as a prayer space. Part V of the article concludes that there are two primary religious responses regarding the validity of prayer in the metaverse. The first response rejects the legitimacy of performing prayer in the metaverse, while the second accepts it under the condition that the virtual space meets the criteria necessary to serve as a legitimate place of worship.

II. CONCEPTUALISATION OF METAVERSE ACCORDING TO QUR'AN

The metaverse is a concept and term first introduced in Neal Stephenson's novel *Snow Crash* in 1992.¹¹ Metaverse, or extended virtual world, is a combination of the words "meta," which refers to virtual and transcendent concepts, and "universe," which means world and universe.¹² The metaverse is a new type of internet application and social form that integrates the latest technologies. It combines virtual and physical reality to create a cyberspace community, which allows real-life habits to be presented in a virtual environment. In this context, activities such as communication, travel, shopping, and daily work activities can take place continuously.¹³

The metaverse is also a space where interaction with virtual objects in real life can occur. With unlimited capabilities in the virtual world, this space can generate interactions between virtual and real worlds with real-time information.¹⁴ Metaverse offers immersive experiences through augmented reality technology, creates a representation of the real world with digital twin technology, builds an economic system using blockchain technology, and integrates the virtual world with the real world in economic, social, and identity systems. It allows any user to create and edit content within the virtual world. The metaverse is still an evolving concept, with various participants contributing to enrich its meaning in their own ways.¹⁵

The metaverse represents a digital universe that is a new generation of internet technology as we know it today. This concept has the potential to change the social life, commercial development, and economy of the internet, which will shape the future of the internet.¹⁶ However, it is important to realise that the existence of the metaverse as a product of humans will not be able to replace the real state of the universe which is a product of the Almighty as Allah swt. said, in Qur'an Surah Az-Dhariyat: 47-49:

¹¹ Songlee Han and Taejong Kim, 'News Big Data Analysis of 'Metaverse' Using Topic Modeling Analysis' (2021) 22 (7) *Journal of Digital Contents Society* 1091, 1099.

¹² Sang Min Park and Young Gab Kim, 'A Metaverse: Taxonomy, Components, Applications, and Open Challenges' (2022) 10 *IEEE* 4209.

¹³ Hakan Yüksel, 'Yeni Medya ve Dijital Dönüşümün Ötesi 'Metaverse' (in Turkey) ['New Media and Beyond Digital Transformation Metaverse'] (2022) 0 (29) *Kafkas Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi* 237, 258.

¹⁴ Gregor Pryor and Stephen Sessa, 'Reed Smith Guide to the Metaverse' (2022) 1 (1) *ReedSmith Perspectives* <<https://www.reedsmith.com/en/perspectives/Metaverse>> accessed 18 June 2024.

¹⁵ Huansheng Ning and others, 'A Survey on Metaverse: The State-of-the-Art, Technologies, Applications, and Challenges' (2021) <<http://arxiv.org/abs/2111.09673>> accessed 24 June 2024.

¹⁶ Yong Li and Dan Xiong, 'The Metaverse Phenomenon in the Teaching of Digital Media Art Major' (2021) 643 *Proceedings of the 2021 Conference on Art and Design: Inheritance and Innovation* 348, 353.

“The heavens We have built with Our hands and We have indeed expanded them. (47) The earth We spread out. (We are) the best of those who spread. (48) We have created everything in pairs so that you may remember (the greatness of Allah)(49).”¹⁷

Based on this verse, Allah, the Almighty, makes clear His power in creating the universe. That is, "We built it by hand (Our power)" According to Buya Hamka in *Tafsir Al-Azhar*, Volume 8, it means that:

"Hand" here means unequalled power. This is one of the most protracted discussions among the schools of thought in Islam. The hand of Allah Himself made and created all of this world, which is His infinite power."¹⁸

The word "ayd(in)" is the plural of "yad" which means hand. Many scholars interpret this word as a symbol of power.¹⁹ This verse explains that Allah SWT has created the sky in a beautiful form, which reflects the majesty of His power. The sky was lifted up by His power and made like a high and firm roof.²⁰ And Allah has power over everything; He never gets tired, sluggish, or exhausted.²¹

Implicitly, this verse refutes the Jewish claim that Allah created the heavens and the earth in six days, but on the seventh day rested and lay down on His 'Throne due to exhaustion.²² The word 'heaven' appears frequently in various verses of the Qur'an. In some verses, this word refers to the meaning of the universe.²³ This is also true in the above-mentioned verse. The universe is not a static entity; rather, it is dynamic, constantly changing and evolving. This understanding has become clearer after the rapid advances in astronomy.

This situation was actually mentioned in the Qur'ān 14 centuries ago, at a time when the science of astronomy was still very limited.²⁴ Allah states, "And We indeed expanded it," meaning We made the firmament wide and high without the support of pillars. We also levelled the earth, making it an expanse for all creatures. In other words, We have created the earth in the best way possible for its inhabitants.²⁵ We have created everything in pairs. This includes all aspects of creation, such as earth and sky, night and day, sun and moon, land and

¹⁷ Qur'an Surah Az-zariat (The Winnowing Winds) 47:49 [Ministry of Religious Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia. h.95].

¹⁸ Prof. Dr. Hamka, *Tafsir Al-Azhar* (in Arabic) [*Al-Azhar Commentary*] Volume 8 (Jakarta: Gema Insani 2015) 496.

¹⁹ Fahru Reza Hakim, 'Makna Lafaz 'Yad' Yang Disematkan Kepada Allah Dalam Al-Qur'an (Studi Komparatif Penafsiran Antara Metode Takwil, Tafwīdh dan Al-Itsbat' (in Indonesian) ['The Attributes to Allah in the Qur'an (Comparative Study of Interpretation Between the Methods of Takwil, Tafwīdh and Al-Itsbat)'] <<https://repository.ptiq.ac.id/id/eprint/1187>> accessed 12 June 2024.

²⁰ L Artikasari, 'Makna Tangan Allah Menurut Tafsir Al-Sa'dī dan Tafsir Al-Marāghī' (in Indonesia) ['The Meaning of Allah's Hand According to Tafsir Al-Sa'dī and Tafsir Al-Marāghī'] *IAIN Ponorogo* (2022) <<https://etheses.iainponorogo.ac.id/20929/>> accessed 12 June 2024.

²¹ Jamil, *Hukum-Hukum Ketuhanan Cetakan Ke-I* (in Indonesian) [*Divine Laws, First Edition*] (Medan: Cv. Manhaj Medan, 2019) 67

²² Benedict Bin Sisom and Alwyn C. Hendriks, 'Pemahaman Tentang Sabat Lunar Berdasarkan Imamat 23:3 Di Gmahk Mountain View Church Kota Belud Sabah Malaysia' (in Indonesian) ['Understanding of the Lunar Sabbath Based on Leviticus 23:3 at Gmahk Mountain View Church, Kota Belud, Sabah, Malaysia'] (2018) 10 (1) *Jurnal Koinonia* 61, 87.

²³ Heru Juabdin Sada, 'Alam semesta dalam perspektif al-qur'an dan hadist' (in Indonesian) ['The Universe in the Perspective of the Qur'an and Hadith'] (2016) 7 *Al-Tadzkiyyah: Jurnal Pendidikan Islam* 102, 119.

²⁴ Esti Widayanti Yuli, 'Analisis Materi Astronomi pada Pembelajaran Sains' (in Indonesian) ['Analysis of Astronomy Material in Science Learning'] (2013) 1 (1) *Journal of Islamic Religious Education* 140, 160.

²⁵ Lukman, 'Generation of Muslims Rahmatan Lil Alamin with Scientific Approach' (2015) *SeIPTI* 141, 152.

sea, light and darkness, faith and disbelief, life and death, happiness and sorrow, and heaven and hell. This principle also applies to all living creatures and vegetation

However, it is understood that the concept of the metaverse is often associated with visions of a more sophisticated internet future, where the boundaries between the physical and virtual worlds are eroded.²⁶ However, it should be noted that the definition and scope of the metaverse is still evolving along with technological developments and interpretations from various communities and industries.

The metaverse creates a virtual ecosystem that engages users in immersive multimedia experiences, covering aspects of life such as social interaction, commerce, education, entertainment and more. The development of the metaverse is leading to the creation of a more complex and globally connected virtual world, creating a digital space that is continuous and ever evolving but cannot yet replace the role and position of Allah, the Almighty, in regulating the interaction of human life in the world.

III. POTENTIAL DIFFERENCES BETWEEN AHL AL-HADITH AND AHL AL-RA'YI VIEWS ON PRAYER IN THE METAVERSE

A. Views Of Ahl-Ra'yi

The issue of prayer in the metaverse is a new terminology in the view of Ahl al-Ra'yi. However, based on their methodology of deriving rulings, Ahl al-Ra'yi might assert that if metaverse technology can fulfill the conditions and pillars of prayer, such as virtual purity and the accurate determination of the Qibla direction virtually, then prayer in the metaverse may be considered valid.²⁷

Ahl al-Ra'yi might look at the purpose and essence of prayer, which is to proclaim the greatness of Allah and establish a relationship with Him, in this case the solemnity of the prayer, and then see if it can be performed properly in the metaverse.

Ahl al-Ra'yi would critically evaluate the possibility of performing prayers in the metaverse. In this regard, factors such as the ability of technology to create profound spiritual experiences, awareness of the virtual environment, and the presence of elements that allow individuals to feel a spiritual connection with Allah are considered.

Ahl al-Ra'yi will be prepared to address changes in technology and ways of worship that may arise in this digital age. They will seek ways to integrate Islamic principles in their understanding of technological developments such as the metaverse, while retaining the essence and traditional values in the performance of worship.²⁸

B. Views of Ahl al-Hadith

The metaverse is not considered a valid place to pray because it does not fulfil the conditions of prayer stipulated in the Hadith, such as the sanctity of the place and physically facing the

²⁶ Simon Elias Bibri and Zaheer Allam, 'The Metaverse as a Virtual Form of Data-Driven Smart Cities: The Ethics of the Hyper-Connectivity, Datafication, Algorithmization, and Platformization of Urban Society' (2022) 2 (1) Computational Urban Science 1, 22.

²⁷ Ansori Ansori and Munawir Munawir, 'Ahl Al-Hadis and Ahl Al-Ra'y (A Polemic of Domination Dynamics on Hadith)' (2022) 6 AL QUDS : Jurnal Studi Alquran dan Hadis.

²⁸ Firdaus Firdaus and others, 'Various Methods of Establishing Contemporary Islamic Law' (2020) 10 Ulumuddin : Jurnal Ilmu-ilmu Keislaman 39.

Qibla. Prayers in the metaverse may be considered invalid if the interactions in it do not fulfil the correct movements and recitations of the prayer.²⁹

Ahl al-Hadith would emphasise the importance of adhering to the teachings that have been described in the Qur'an and Hadith in relation to the procedures of prayer. They would refer to these sacred texts to determine the conditions that must be met for a prayer to be considered valid, including the correct movements and recitation.

In their approach, Ahl al-Hadith will tend to maintain the Islamic traditions that have been passed down from previous generations. They may be sceptical of new innovations or interpretations in worship and would prefer to maintain the practice of prayer according to the traditionally taught procedures.³⁰

IV. THE VALIDITY OF THE METAVERSE AS A PRAYER SPACE

The issue of prayer in Islam is closely related to time and place, as these two elements play an important role in fulfilling religious obligations correctly and legally.³¹ In Islam, the times of prayer have been strictly determined and must be obeyed by every Muslim. The five daily prayer times, namely Fajr, Zuhr, Asr, Maghrib and Isha, have specific schedules based on the position of the sun. In Qur'an, Surah An-Nisa':103, Allah SWT says:

.... إِنَّ الصَّلَاةَ كَانَتْ عَلَى الْمُؤْمِنِينَ كِتَابًا مَوْقُوتًا

Translation:

“Verily, prayer is an obligation whose time has been fixed upon the believers.”³²

This verse emphasises that every Muslim should perform prayers at the appointed times. Each prayer time has a specific time span that must be adhered to, and this helps to keep the rhythm of daily life in a spiritual frame.

As in the hadith of the prophet narrated by An-nasai (Meaning):

“Jabir bin Abdullah (may Allah be pleased with him) reported that the Prophet was visited by Jibril (peace be upon him) and said to him, "Get up and pray." So he performed the Zhuhr prayer when the sun slipped. Then Asr time approached and Jibril said, "Get up and pray." So he prayed Asr when the length of the shadow of the object was equal to the length of the object. Then Maghrib time approached and Jibril said, "Get up and pray." So he prayed Maghrib when the sun set. Then the time of Isha` approached and Gabriel said, "Get up and pray." So, he prayed Isha` when the *shafaq* (red mega) disappeared. Then the time of Fajr approached and Gabriel said, "Get up and pray." So, he prayed the Fajr prayer when dawn broke”.³³

Even though users are in a virtual world, they are still bound by the prayer schedule that applies in the real world. This means that when the prayer time arrives according to the

²⁹ Ahmad Farhan Subhi, M Hasbi Umar and Ramlah, *Dinamika Hukum Islam (in Indonesia)[Dynamics of Islamic Law]* (2023) 3 *Jurnal Indragiri Penelitian Multidisiplin* 37.

³⁰ Muhammad Ikhsan and Azwar Iskandar, ‘Inter-Religious Interaction From The Perspective of Hadith As A Source of Islamic Law’ (2022) 5 *Al-Bukhari : Jurnal Ilmu Hadis* 71

³¹ Khoirul Abror, *Fiqh Ibadah (in Indonesia) [Islamic Worship Jurisprudence]* (Yogyakarta: CV Arjasa Pratama Bandar Lampung 2019) 11.

³² Qur'an Surah An-nisa (Woman) 4:103 [Ministry of Religious Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia. h.95]

³³ Al Nasai, *Sunan Al Nasai*. Volume 1 (Damascus: Maktabah Tijariyah Kubro 1930). Hadith number 427, 263.

schedule applicable in the user's physical location, they must pause from their virtual activities to perform the prayer. Metaverse, with its advanced technology, can provide a prayer time reminder feature that is synchronised with the user's time zone and geographical position in the real world. This feature will help users to keep their prayer obligations in mind, despite being engrossed in virtual activities.

While the metaverse provides an immersive and interactive virtual environment, it cannot serve as a legitimate space for prayer because it does not reflect real physical conditions. In Islam, the act of prayer requires a physical location that adheres to specific criteria, such as cleanliness and purity from impurities. Additionally, prayer must be performed facing the Qibla in Makkah, a physical orientation that is essential. Although the metaverse can simulate the direction of the Qibla and create a virtual space that appears clean and pure, it still falls short of fulfilling the physical requirements necessary for Islamic prayer.

One of the main reasons is that virtual space in the metaverse has no real physical existence. In the context of Islamic law, the cleanliness and sanctity of the place of prayer is an aspect that cannot be ignored. The Messenger of Allah (SAW) said:

عَنْ جَابِرِ بْنِ عَبْدِ اللَّهِ ، رَضِيَ اللَّهُ عَنْهُمَا ، قَالَ : قَالَ رَسُولُ اللَّهِ ، صَلَّى اللَّهُ عَلَيْهِ وَسَلَّمَ : أُعْطِيتُ خَمْسًا لَمْ يُعْطَهُنَّ أَحَدٌ مِنَ الْأَنْبِيَاءِ قَبْلِي: نُصِرْتُ بِالرُّعْبِ مَسِيرَةَ شَهْرٍ ، وَجُعِلَتْ لِي الْأَرْضُ مَسْجِدًا وَطَهْرًا ، وَأَيُّمَا رَجُلٍ مِنْ أُمَّتِي أَدْرَكَتْهُ الصَّلَاةُ فَلْيُصَلِّ ، وَأَجَلْتُ لِي الْعَنَائِمَ ، وَكَانَ النَّبِيُّ يُبْعَثُ إِلَى قَوْمِهِ خَاصَّةً ، وَبُعِثْتُ إِلَى النَّاسِ كَافَّةً ، وَأُعْطِيتُ الشَّقَاعَةَ . رواه البخاري

Meaning:

“Jabir ibn Abdullah reported that the Messenger of Allah said: "I have been given five things that were not given to any prophet before me: (1) I have been helped by the fear of my enemies from a distance of a month's journey, (2) the earth has been made for me as a place of prostration and a means of purification, so wherever anyone of my people finds the time for prayer has come, he should perform it, (3) it has been made lawful for me the spoils of war that have never been made lawful for any Prophet before me, (4) it has been given to me the right to intercede, and (5) in the past the Prophets were sent only to their people, while I have been sent to all people”³⁴

This Hadith shows that prayer can be performed in any place as long as the place is clean and pure. However, the purity in question is physical purity, which cannot be represented by a virtual simulation. Therefore, while the metaverse can provide a visual experience that resembles a mosque or other sacred space, it cannot fulfil the physical requirements of cleanliness and sanctity demanded by the Shariah.

In the metaverse, although an environment can be designed to look like a mosque or other holy place, it still has no physical substance that can be held or felt. There is no way to ensure that the virtual environment is free of impurities as it has no physical substance that can be cleaned or assessed for cleanliness.

In addition, physical presence is also important in terms of the social and communal aspects of congregational prayer. Praying in congregation in a mosque or other visible place strengthens the social and spiritual bonds among worshipers. Rasulullah SAW said:

حَدَّثَنَا يَحْيَى بْنُ يَحْيَى قَالَ: قَرَأْتُ عَلَى مَالِكٍ ، عَنْ نَافِعٍ ، عَنْ ابْنِ عُمَرَ أَنَّ رَسُولَ اللَّهِ ﷺ قَالَ: « صَلَاةُ الْجَمَاعَةِ أَفْضَلُ مِنْ صَلَاةِ الْفَدَى بِسَبْعٍ وَعِشْرِينَ دَرَجَةً »

³⁴ Imam Bukhari, *Sahih Bukhori*, Volume 1 (Damascus: Dar Ibn Kathir, 1993) Hadith No. 427, 168.

Meaning:

"Praying in congregation is twenty-seven degrees better than praying alone."³⁵

Physical presence in the same place allows for real social interactions, such as standing in the same *saf* (line), listening to the imam directly, and feeling a sense of togetherness with other worshippers. This experience cannot be fully replicated in the metaverse, where interactions occur in the form of digital avatars without actual physical presence. Therefore, while the metaverse can be a tool for prayer education and reminders, it cannot replace a real prayer space that meets the requirements of Islamic law.

Metaverse as a virtual space offers the potential to create an environment that can help enhance the solemnity of prayer. In the virtual space, users can design a prayer space that is quiet and free from real-world distractions, which can help focus better on praying.

With metaverse technology enabling the creation of highly personalised and tranquil environments, metaverse can be used to create specially designed prayer spaces to enhance concentration and focus on worship. Users can choose a virtual environment that suits their preferences, such as a room designed to resemble a mosque, or a relaxing nature scene. This could be a way for those who find it difficult to find a conducive place in the real world to still pray solemnly.

However, it is important to remember that while metaverse can help to create a calm environment, it does not remove the need to fulfil the other requirements of prayer, such as the cleanliness of the place and the fulfilment of all the pillars of prayer. As the rule of law reads: *ما لا يتم الواجب إلا به فهو واجب* something that does not complete an obligation is obligatory"³⁶.

Shaykh Ibn 'Uthaymeen (may Allah have mercy on him) was asked about the ruling on closing one's eyes during prayer, especially when reciting Qur'an and when praying the Qunut prayer, with the aim of achieving solemnity in prayer. He gave the following answer:

"The scholars have stated that it is *makrooh* (disliked) to close one's eyes in prayer, except in certain circumstances, such as when there is a distraction in front of the person who is praying or a dazzling light, in which case closing the eyes can be used to avoid such distractions. Meanwhile, the notion that closing one's eyes can increase one's focus in prayer can be regarded as a trick of the devil to cause one to fall into what is *makrooh* without realising it. If a person feels that he can only achieve *khushu* (concentration) by closing his eyes, this can become a wrong habit, where he feels more *khushu* by closing his eyes than by opening them"³⁷.

This application should be considered as an adjunct to enhancing solemnity, and not as a substitute for a physical place of prayer that meets the requirements of Islamic law. Thus, with these stipulations in mind, the virtual space in the metaverse can serve as a tool that supports a more solemn and focused prayer. However, Shaykh Ibn 'Uthaymeen emphasised that:

³⁵ Imam Muslim bin al-Hajjaj al-Qusyairy an-Naisabury, *Sahih Muslim*, Volume 2 (Turkey: Dar Al Taba'a al Amira n.d.) Hadith 650, 122.

³⁶ Tajuddin al Subki, *Al Ibhaj Fii Syarhil Minhaj* (in Arabic) [*The Delight in the Explanation of the Minhaj*] Volume 2 (Ihyau al Turats n.d.) 324.

³⁷ Muhammad bin Shalih al Uthaymeen, *Majmu Fatawa Wa Rasail Al Uthaymeen* (in Arabic) [*Collection of Fatwas and Letters of Al-Uthaymeen*] Volume 13 (Darul Wathan 1413) 299.

“The belief of some people that closing one's eyes can increase *khushu* (concentration) in prayer may be a trick of the Shaytaan that leads one to do something *makrooh* (disliked) without realising it.”

He warned that the solemnity of prayer should not depend on a- disliked action in Shari'ah, such as closing the eyes. If a person accustoms himself to feeling more *khushu* just by closing his eyes, this could be the start of a harmful habit that will lead him to feel that his prayer is only perfect if his eyes are closed.

V. CONCLUSION

This study examines the perspectives of two significant Islamic legal schools of thought, Ahl al-Hadith and Ahl al-Ra'yi, regarding the practice of prayer within the metaverse. As prayer is a fundamental pillar of Islam, its integration into the rapidly evolving digital environment of the metaverse raises critical questions about the validity and legitimacy of such practices. By employing epistemological and ethical frameworks, the research analyses how will these schools respond to the opportunities and challenges posed by incorporating technology into religious observance. The findings reveal a dichotomy in religious responses: one perspective categorically rejects the legitimacy of performing prayer in the metaverse, arguing that the digital environment cannot fulfil the necessary conditions for valid worship.

Conversely, the second perspective accepts the practice of prayer in the metaverse, provided that the virtual space adheres to specific criteria required for a legitimate place of worship. This acceptance hinges on the ability of the virtual environment to meet the traditional standards of a prayer space, such as cleanliness, orientation towards the Qibla, and the presence of a congregation. The study underscores the ongoing tension between maintaining religious traditions and embracing technological innovations, offering insights into how Islamic jurisprudence may adapt to the challenges and possibilities of the digital age.

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